

Annex 2. Logic Data Model

Note: White boxes represent the different origins of data (hospitalizations, demographics, socioeconomic information and supply information); dark grey boxes are catalogues for the units of analysis (hospitals and geographic regions); black boxes represent the joint resulting data set and catalogues for diagnoses and procedures; pale grey boxes represent the final output, which are the performance indicators and modifiers. Connection lines: univocal key identifiers (_id) allow 1 to 1 or 1 to N linkage